

THE ROLE OF TOURISM IN THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND ITS DEVELOPMENT FACTORS.

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Abstract: This article provides information about the role of tourism in the economic development of the country and the factors of its development.

Key words: Tourism, economic development, economy, tourist destinations, national tourism.

Tourism is defined as the departure (travel) of an individual from the place of permanent residence for a period of at least 1 year without engaging in paid activities in the destination (country) for health, educational, professional or other purposes. The history of tourism dates back to the beginning of the 19th century. First, organized tourism from England to France was established (1815). The English priest Thomas Cook, who is considered the founder of tourism, organized the first railway tour in 1843. After that, he established his own tour company and in 1866 sent the first tour groups to the United States. In the East, Ibn Battuta, an Arab traveler, started his journey at the age of 21 and traveled almost all the countries of East and North Africa on foot. The first tourist trips in Movarounnahr became active during the period of Amir Temur and Timurids. Amir Temur was in constant contact with the French king Charles VI and the English king Henry IV. His ambassador came to Paris in 1403. Spanish Clavijo's book "The Life and Activities of Timur the Great" describes the social life in Movarunnahr and the tourist's desire for Timur's state. Nowadays, tourism has become popular in many countries of the world. Usually, Tourism is organized through tourism organizations along tourism routes. [1]There are many types and forms of tourism (domestic, international, amateur tourism, organized tourism, local travel, long-distance travel, educational tourism, mountain climbing, water tourism, motor tourism, hiking tourism, sports tourism, etc.). The national company "Uzbekturizm" (founded on July 27, 1992) leads the tourism industry in Uzbekistan. The main task of the company is to develop tourism infrastructure, build modern tourist complexes by attracting foreign investment, develop new tourist destinations, expand the range of services, etc. The national company "Uzbekturizm" has developed the following tourist routes depending on the type of travel: classic route (Tashkent,

Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Tashkent; Tashkent, Samarkand, BukharaShahrisabz, Tashkent). This route is the longest. related to visits to monuments and other historical and cultural monuments; ecological tourism direction (Chimyon, Charvok recreation and treatment center, Zomin reserve, reserves in Bukhara region). This direction is connected with visits to specially protected natural areas and places that are ecologically friendly and useful for tourists; the direction of archaeological tourism (along the territory of Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya, Samarkand). This route is the longest in Uzbekistan. aims to get acquainted with the finds and places where archaeological excavations are being conducted; the direction of extreme tourism (through Chimyan, Fergana Valley, Arol Bay, Bukhara, Navoi regions); linear tourism direction (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent) is related to visiting historical and religious monuments in our country. In order to legally regulate relations in the field of tourism, develop the market of tourist services, as well as protect the rights and legal interests of tourists and subjects of tourist activity, Uzbekistan The Law of the Republic "On Tourism" was adopted (August 20, 1999). At the same time, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the state program for the development of tourism in Uzbekistan until 2005" (April 15, 1999) became an important factor in the development of the industry. "Association of Private Tourism Organizations" was established in Tashkent in 1998 by the decision of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to improve tourism organizations and activate the service market of small and medium-sized tourist enterprises, as well as to attract foreign investment to the tourism sector. It works closely with more than 300 tourist enterprises. There is a tourist base "Kumushkon" and a camping complex "Sanzar" in Uzbekistan, which are organizations of the national company "Uzbektourism". At the same time, there are Chorvoq, Chimyon, Beldersoy recreation centers and about a hundred private hotels. [5] The number of hotels in Uzbekistan that can accommodate and serve many tourists is growing. In 1993, Uzbekistan became a member of the World Tourism Organization (WTO; established in 1975), which unites more than 120 countries. Also, Uzbekistan is a member of the presidium of the European Commission of the WTO. It is planned to open a representative office of the World Tourism Organization in Samarkand region within the framework of the "Great Silk Road" project of 2004. The "Great Silk Road" international tourist advertising information on the field of tourism in Uzbekistan. (since 1994), "Business Guide" JUR (in Russian and English) and other public publications are published. In April 2021, a

presentation of Uzbekistan's pilgrimage tourism potential was held in Dagestan. On the instructions of Deputy Prime Minister, Chairman of the State Tourism Development Committee, Aziz Abduhakimov, promotional activities in the direction of "Travel to the Land of Imams" have started in Dagestan. [2]

Tourism is one of the most promising and rapidly developing sectors of the economy. Neither global problems nor terrorist threats can be an obstacle for tourism. Because it has already become an integral part of human life. According to the World Tourism Organization, in 2019, the number of international tourist visits worldwide reached 1 billion 460 million, while the income from international tourism exceeded 1 trillion 481 billion US dollars. 330 million people are employed in this sector. Between 2009 and 2019, income from international tourism increased by 54%. This means more than the increase in the world gross national product (44%). Many countries, including Uzbekistan, have recognized the tourism sector as one of the priority areas of national economic development. Because tourism contributes to the growth of GDP, the increase of foreign exchange earnings and investments, the development of industry, trade and social infrastructure. In today's world, tourism is an important sector of the economy. Many scientists have conducted research on the impact of the tourism sector on the socio-economic development of the country. For example, A.M. Gudratli positively assessed the impact of tourism on the country's economy, increasing the national income of the tourism sector; creation of new jobs; development of all sectors related to the production of tourist services; development of social and industrial infrastructure in tourist centers; activation of the activities of folk crafts and cultural centers; ensuring an increase in the standard of living of the population; states that it helps to increase foreign exchange earnings[1]. And A. V. Strelnikov found that creating one new job in this network is 20 times cheaper than in the industrial network [2].

Today, tourism is one of the fastest growing and leading industries in terms of income. In recent years, tourism has become a major contributor to world exports and accounts for 11% of global GDP. Over the past 40 years, the number of tourists visiting other countries has increased 20 times, the income from tourism has increased 60 times, and the income from international tourism has reached 400 billion dollars. In particular, deepening the liberalization of the economy, modernization of the country, and sustainable development of all sectors, especially tourism, which is one of the leading sectors of the service sector, are the basis of the success achieved in Uzbekistan. Tourism is the main

driver of world civilization, and nowadays travel is the basis of human goals. In particular, prospects for the development of national tourism will help to increase the position of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan in the world market. As a proof of our opinion, we believe that it is permissible to point out that today great progress is being made in the field of tourism, it is increasing rapidly, new hotels are being built, the number of working places is increasing, the number of qualified specialists is increasing, and the flow of tourists is increasing year by year. Of course, taking into account the favorable climatic conditions and unique landscape of Uzbekistan, there are all grounds for the development of sports and ecological tourism. The Fergana Valley and Tashkent region are rich in magnificent mountain systems, blooming valleys and magnificent mountain rivers. The clean air of the mountain, the abundance of sunny days throughout the year, and the wonderful mountain scenery allow not only the citizens of Uzbekistan, but also the residents of neighboring countries such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan to become tourist objects. Various types of mineral waters are widespread in Uzbekistan, many people visit more than 300 healing underground mineral water sources in the country. Currently, 121 of these sources are operating. [4] There are several mountain resorts, such as Chimyon and Tortkol, where it is possible to develop mountain skiing. High snow mountains allow to realize different types of mountain tourism, such as mountaineering, speleotourism, river tourism. The abundance of medicinal herbs provides an opportunity to organize different ecological types, different herbs and species for collecting plants. This arouses interest among many foreign tourists. Assessing the current state of tourism, it is important to note that the level of infrastructure development in Uzbekistan does not fully meet the needs of foreign tourists. The underdevelopment of the infrastructure is caused by the previous administrative-command system, which did not allow to encourage competition and improvement. If the infrastructure is not sufficiently developed, it is impossible to increase the flow of tourists and, accordingly, to increase foreign exchange earnings. Based on this, the state of the infrastructure has a direct impact on the development of tourism and the formation of the country's image. First of all, it should be noted that until the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, not enough attention was paid to tourism. There was no objective information and advertising about the tourist potential of the republic. It can be said that the tourism, service and entertainment infrastructure is not developed, the level of service to tourists is low, and there are no contacts with the world's leading tourist enterprises. Currently, tourism

infrastructure is not evenly distributed in the territory of Uzbekistan. 36% of the republic's tourism potential is concentrated in Tashkent city and region. The region (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Khorezm) and the city of Tashkent have a large infrastructure potential, Fergana Valley has 19% of tourism infrastructure. Among the economists in Uzbekistan are M. Pardaev, R. Atabaev, I.S. Tukhliev, F.Kh. Kudratov, N. Tukhliev, T. Abdullaeva, A.S. Soliev, M.R. Usmanov, M.M. Mukhammedov, D.K. Usmanova, M. Khoshimov, A. Norchaev, B. Turaev, O. Kh.Khamidov, A.A.Eshtaev have conducted scientific research in the field of tourism [2]. Tourism, as a component of the economy, brings income to the host country, provides high foreign exchange earnings, and increases the level of employment of the population. A hotel will be needed to serve tourists. They have to eat here. They enter and participate in various performances. In many cases, if they are foreign tourists, it provides an increase in foreign exchange earnings. Tourism is not only an economic, but also an important social sphere. Along with its economic efficiency, it also has great moral, spiritual and intellectual importance. Due to this, the state pays special attention to this sector and sets certain benefits. People use these benefits just because they are tourists. This also indicates the unique nature of tourism and its great socio-economic importance. Privileges are manifested when tourists pass through customs posts, pay taxes, allow their passports when leaving the country, get tickets for air and railway transport, and process them. Tourism also has great benefits for the local population. They will be provided with work, they will communicate with representatives of different nationalities, peoples and peoples and get acquainted with their different traditions and values, they will have the opportunity to earn a permanent income, they will have the opportunity to sell products, the local population will keep their traditions as much as possible. and to show their values, they preserve it and restore the forgotten ones, while reviving the attractive traditions of hospitality, they improve the traditions of hospitality. In the end, the outlook and cultural level of the local population will increase steadily. The development of tourism is also very useful for the state. In particular, due to the development of tourism, he achieves the rise of the Oz economy, ensures an increase in revenues to the state budget, achieves the preservation of natural resources, tries to ensure the social stability of the country and achieves it, achieves international relations, expands cultural relations, increases foreign exchange earnings, etc. Tourism can have both positive and negative effects on the lives of local residents. Its positive features include: creation of jobs; increase of income, increase of standard of

living of local population; acceleration of the urbanization process, development of urban services, infrastructure, cultural organizations; acceleration of social and cultural processes; creation of local cultural centers, development of folk art, traditions, customs; increase in demand for agricultural products and locally produced goods; restoration and protection of local cultural monuments; expansion of natural complexes; increasing the attractiveness of the region; revitalization of local cultural life; The negative features are as follows: - increase in the share of unskilled labor; - increase in violations of public norms (drinking, prostitution, hooliganism); - "erosion" of the family (family separations, disagreements, etc.) - between local residents and tourists, etc. Analyzing the development of tourism in Uzbekistan, we can observe that the attention to the field of tourism in our country has increased and the number of visitors has increased. Economic results of tourism development in Uzbekistan [3] . Separation of essentials among certain groups of a huge variety of trips is that the concrete type of tourism largely determines the set of services by type, pricing. The nature of the travel organizer's activity, the nature of the host region, and many other parameters that take the place of the leading activities in marketing and tourism business management. The most common indicators for the classification of international tourism are the type of offer, the method of organizing the trip, the purpose of the trip, and the method of movement. Leisure and recreational tourism includes various types of tourism for the purpose of recreation, sightseeing, sports, exotic vacations, thematic trips. In the classification by type of offers, group and individual foreign tourism is understood. In the tourism business, there are a number of terms that professionals understand each other half-heartedly. The terms FIT and GROUP are the most commonly used terms. FIT foreign independent traveler is called individual tourist in Russian. He sets the itinerary and schedule of the trip as he pleases. A single tourist can use the service of a travel agency. But it is also possible to organize a trip independently. For example, through the Internet. Complex service is the main type of services offered for group tourism. A tourist buys a tour package. It contains a set of services included in the tour price. Usually the price of the tour package is lower than the sum of the value of some services included in the tour package. The group tour package is issued with a group voucher. Tourists of the group receive comprehensive services in return. This includes air transportation, hotel accommodation, catering, excursions and other services. Classification according to the organization of the trip. Organized tourism is a trip organized by a tourist company for individual or group tourists.

Organized tourists have the right to purchase tour packages with various services from tour operators or their agents. Tourist infrastructure includes hotels, catering establishments, a set of communication routes, communications, organizations, shops, sports facilities and is closely connected with tourist service enterprises. It is aimed at ensuring the necessary conditions of the tourist infrastructure, the safety and health of tourists. In conclusion, it can be said that today tourism is recognized as one of the most profitable industries. In this regard, many countries are developing a number of programs for the development of tourism. The tourism sector also has great potential in increasing the economic potential of our country. Tourism will become one of the leading industries in our country as a result of the work carried out mainly on the development of international tourism.

In short, tourism plays an important role in the socio-economic development of the country. For this reason, in order to further increase the level of socio-economic development of the country, it is necessary to form complex, interconnected mechanisms of using tourism potential.

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